

MEAT PRODUCTIVITY OF SIMMENTAL BULLS BELONGING TO DIFFERENT PRODUCTION TYPES

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Abstract. In the article, the data on the effect of intensive breeding and fattening of Simmental bulls of different production types on the parameters of meat productivity are highlighted.

The live weight of bulls after weaning was 508.9 kg in group II (meat-milk type), and compared to group I (milk-meat type), it prevailed by 29.5 kg or 5.8% ($R \leq 0.001$). Also, live weight before slaughter was higher by 29.7 kg or 6.5 %, ($R \leq 0.01$), respectively. Bulls of the II group (meat-milk type) prevailed by 20.0 kg or 7.4% ($R \leq 0.05$). A 0.7% advantage was observed in bulls of the II group in terms of slaughter yield.

Examining Meatni grade (according to DST 7595-55) bulls, the first grade portion in group II was 98.1 kg, this figure was 89.0 kg in group I, and bulls in group II weighed 9.1 kg (10.2 %) showed a high rate. When the bulls of the second grade were studied, it was 21.4 kg in group II and 22.1 kg in group I , while the weight of bulls in the second group was 0.7 kg or 3.2% less. Bulls of the third grade were 8.5 kg in group II and 9.4 kg in group I , and 0.9 kg or 9.6% less was observed in bulls of the second group. From these data, it can be seen that high-quality meat was obtained in large quantities from bulls of the II group (meat-milk type). This is an

indication that in the production type cross-section of bulls, the meat-milk type bulls give more quality meat.

Keywords. Livestock, beef, Simmental, breed, production types, bull, live weight, carcass weight, DST 7595-55, DST 5110-87, carcass yield, visceral fat, muscles, lamb, meat index, etc.

Enter. Animal husbandry, especially cattle breeding, plays an important role in satisfying human demand for milk and meat products.

Beef is a combination of muscle, bone and fat and connective tissue. According to the parts separated from the meat , it is divided into red meat, that is, the part separated from the meat, and muscle, that is, the part separated from the bone, connective fat tissue, and lymph nodes. A certain amount of adipose tissue remains in the muscle even when it is separated, which is between the muscles and gives the lean meat a marbled appearance or quality . As a food product, muscle and adipose tissue is a valuable part. Meat 98% muscle, fat binder and bone texture organize does. The rest consists of blood, nerves and other tissues.

Many factors affect the meat productivity of cattle. If we look at the scientific sources published in recent years on the production of products in cattle breeding, we can see that in most cases, importance is attached to their constitution types, especially "Production types".

Meat productivity indicators of cattle are determined live and after slaughter. Live weight, absolute and daily growth, fatness level, and feed coverage characteristics of cattle are the main parameters that determine the meatiness of cattle during life. indicators such as obesity level are determined and cattle are divided into obesity categories. This event is useful in characterizing the quantity and quality of meat, fattening of which is important in determining slaughter periods.

Live weight is divided into: weight at birth, live weight after fattening is the weight before taking animals to the barn at the end of fattening, pre-slaughter weight is the weight after 24 hours of starvation before slaughter, during which water is not

stopped. The last two weights are considered important in scientific research and experimental work. Watering of cattle is limited only 2 hours before slaughtering.

According to [10;C.19-20], the Simmental breed, like other dairy and mixed cattle breeds, has interbreeding types, and mainly meat-milk type animals are used for meat production. The authors studied the live weight of first-born cows of the milk, milk-meat and meat-milk types in the conditions of 4 "Sverdlov", "Karl Marks", "Mir" and "Experimental" farms of the Orenburg region. Animals of various types in the section of farms: 507.0; 553.3; 610.7; 521.8; 535.1; 534.6; 408.0; 492.0; 543.4; 500.0; Live weight was 536.3 and 584.4.

[9; C. 407], [4; C. 9-12] stated that the breeding and fattening of meat-milk type cattle for the production of meat of sufficient quality from young cattle of the Simmental breed gives good results. Simmentals of this type are superior to other production types by 5.0-6.8% in weight and 4.0-7.1% in slaughter yield.

[11;C.8-10] crossbreeding Simmental breed with Montbelyard and Holstein breeds is of great interest. The authors conducted simple and complex crossbreeding of the purebred Simmental breed and its hybrid offspring of different genotypes with selected breeds . A control slaughter at 18 months showed that the purebred Simmental gained 4.9-33.3 kg more live weight than its peers . They prevailed in terms of meat weight, 9.4-47.1 kg . Slaughter yield was 58.2% in purebred Simmental, while hybrid bulls of different genotypes obtained as a result of crossing: 57.7%; 56.8; 56.9; It was 55.6, 53.6, 52.4 and 51.8%.

[5;C.17-18] fed Simmental (n=62) and local (n=53) heifers of German selection from birth to 18 months. In terms of live weight at 18 months, the cattle belonging to the German selection surpassed their peers of the domestic selection by 20.6 kg (6.50%).

Legoshin G.P. (2017), Kibkalo L.I. (1995), Baymukanov D.A. (2017) studies, it has been proved that the economic benefits of growing and fattening young cattle

up to 18 months in intensive technology. At this age, it is possible to grow quality meat from cattle.

[1; S. 3-11, 3; S. 2-3, 7; S. 11-12, 12; 47-49, 13; P.18-21] concluded that the feeding conditions of young cattle have a great influence on their growth and development.

The purpose of the study. Study of meat productivity indicators of Simmental breed bulls of different production types reared in intensive technology.

Research object and applied methods. Simmental bulls of various production types bred at "Sardoba Railway Agro-Industrial Complex" LLC, Mirzaabad District, Syrdarya Region.

The guidelines of DST 5110-87 and DST 7579-55 were used for dividing the bulls into fatness categories and graded sections according to the degree of fatness, live weight was determined on scales before transportation, transportation and after fasting. In order to study the parameters of meat productivity in the slaughterhouse, a control slaughter was carried out on 3 bulls from each group . Carcass weight, carcass weight, muscle, fat, bone and tendon, tendon and ligament weight were determined by weighing. Based on the obtained data, carcass yield, meat yield, internal fat yield, bone and tendons, tendons and ligaments, and meatiness indices were calculated using generally accepted methods.

Research results and analysis. Currently (DST 5110-87), according to the state standard, the degree of fatness of cattle is divided into 2 categories: first and second category (category). If the level of fatness is not specified during the life, then the level of fatness is determined according to the state standard after the animal is slaughtered. In the research, we tried to study the indicators of liveability and meat productivity after slaughter of bulls of different production types raised in intensive technology.

When we estimated the live time with fall, it was found that the bulls in both groups belong to the first obesity category. In order to more accurately evaluate the

level of obesity and to study the meat productivity of bulls, we performed a control slaughter of 3 bulls from each group. We took the bulls to the slaughterhouse in A. Temur street , Zangiota district, Tashkent region for control slaughter . The transportation distance to Koshkhana was 150 km and duration was 3 hours. It is known that animals partially lose weight during transportation. When we observed this process in our experiments, we witnessed the following. The bulls were weighed at the farm before being loaded into the vehicle. This event was also carried out when the bulls were brought to the aviary. Bulls brought to the aviary were starved for 21 hours until slaughter. Thus, the period until the bulls were slaughtered according to zootechnical standards was 24 hours in total. Watering of bulls was stopped 2 hours before slaughter. After that, the control bulls were slaughtered. The obtained results are presented in the table below.

Table 1

Results of control slaughter of bulls at 18 months, ($X \pm S_x$)

Indicators	Group ($p = 3$)	
	I	II
Live weight after fattening, kg	479.4±2.07	508.9±2.87 ***
Live weight before slaughter, kg	455.3 ± 5.70	485.0 ± 7.51 **
Live weight loss to slaughter: kg	24.1	23.9
	5.3	4.9
%		
Uncooled weight, kg	241.0 ± 5.21	259.3 ± 5.36 *
What is the outcome, %	53.0	53.5
Internal fat weight, kg	11.0 ± 0.58	12.7 ± 0.33
Internal oil yield, %	2.4	2.6

Carcass weight, kg	252.0 ± 5.78	272.0 ± 5.59 *
Slaughter yield, %	55.3	56.0

Comment: * $R \leq 0.05$, ** $R \leq 0.01$, *** $R \leq 0.001$

Table 1 Live weight of bulls after fattening during transport (150 km, 3 hours) and during storage to slaughter (21 hours) 24.1 kg (5.3%) in group I and 23.9 kg (4.9%) in group II was found to have lost live weight. Live weight of bulls after weaning was 508.9 kg in group II (meat-milk type) and 479.4 kg in group I (milk-meat type), and bulls in the second group were 29.5 kg or 5.8% more than their counterparts in the first group. ($R \leq 0.001$) prevailed. Also, live weight before slaughter was higher by 29.7 kg or 6.5 % ($R \leq 0.01$). The weight of unchilled meat obtained from the slaughter of bulls was 259.3 kg in group II, which was higher by 18.3 kg or 7.6% ($R \leq 0.05$) compared to group I. It was observed that the yield of uncooled nitrogen was 0.5% higher in group II . It was found that the amount of visceral fat from the slaughter of bulls was 1.7 kg or 15.4% higher in bulls of group II.

Another important indicator of meat productivity is carcass weight. According to this indicator, bulls of the II group (meat-milk type) showed an advantage over their counterparts of the I group (milk-meat) by 20.0 kg or 7.4% ($R \leq 0.05$). A 0.7% advantage was observed in bulls of the II group in terms of slaughter yield. High slaughter yield and heavy meat yield were observed from bulls of both production types.

In the conducted research, we studied the morphological composition of the meat meat obtained from the slaughter of bulls, the obtained data are given in table 2 below .

Table 2

Morphological composition of meat meat.

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Group (p = 3)</i>	
	<i>I</i>	<i>II</i>
Weight of uncooled meat, kg	241.0 $\pm$ 5.21	259.3 $\pm$ 5.36 *
Weight of cooled meat, kg	237.0 $\pm$ 4, 62	256, 3 $\pm$ 5, 36 *
Lost on cooling		
Weight of the item: kg	4.0	3.0
%	1.6	1.2
Muscles, kg	175.8	190, 8
%	74, 2	74, 4
Oil, kg	10.6	12.1
%	4, 5	4.7
Bone and tendons, kg	42.0	44.5
%	17, 7	17, 4
Sinew and joints, kg	7, 8	7.9
%	3.3	3.1
losses, kg	0.8	1.0
%	0.3	0, 4
Meat index	4.18	4.29

Comment: * $R \leq 0.05$

of Table 2 that the weight of the cooled meat was 256.3 kg in bulls of the II group of meat-milk type, while their equal weight was 237.0 kg in bulls of the I group of milk-meat type, compared to them by 19.3 kg or 8. It was 1% higher. Meat's muscle tissue is the most valuable part of the meat. When the muscles were separated from Meat, it was found that 15.0 kg or 8.5% more muscle tissue was obtained in the bulls of the II group compared to the bulls of the I group. A high percentage of muscle tissue in both groups (74.2-74.4%) indicates a high level of meat productivity.

When evaluating the meat productivity of bulls, it is possible to make a conclusion about the meat index by knowing the amount of bones, tendons, and tendons. No significant difference was observed between bulls in both groups. When the meat index was evaluated, it was confirmed once again that bulls in both groups belonged to the first obesity category . That is, compared to 1 kg of bone tissue,

muscle tissue in group I corresponded to 4.18 and in group II 4.29 kg. This means that the body of the bulls is full of muscle at a good level.

In order to make a more accurate assessment of the meat quality of bulls, we studied the amount of lean meat and bone and body parts in a half-carcass. The obtained data are summarized in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3

The amount of skin and bone in the half body

Body parts	Group (p=3)							
	I				II			
	Red meat		Bone		Red meat		Bone	
	kg	%	kg	%	kg	%	kg	%
Neck	7.6	7.6	1.8	8.6	6.6	6.2	1.9	8.9
Shoulders	17.7	17.7	4.4	20.0	17.1	16.03	4.3	20.1
Back and ribs	27.6	27.6	7.5	39.0	33.1	31.04	8.3	38.8
Waist	9.3	9.3	1.3	6.2	9.2	8.63	1.3	6.1
Pelvis	37.8	37.8	5.5	26.2	40.6	38.1	5.6	26.1
Total	100.0	100	20.5	100	106.6	100	21.4	100

As can be seen from the data of Table 3, there is an advantage in bulls of the II group of meat-milk type in terms of half-body weight. This amount difference was 7.5 kg (6.2%). Also, the lean part of the half-carcass weight was 100.0 kg or 82.9% in bulls of the I group of milk-meat type, and the bone part was 20.5 kg or 17.1%, while in the bulls of the II group of meat-milk type it was 106.6 kg or 83.3% of the meat and 21.4 kg or 16.7% of the bone. We can see that both groups have a high level of meat filling in the neck, shoulder-shoulder, back and ribs, waist, and hip parts. One of the indicators of the quality of meat is flour. We observed the following when we studied the meat of bulls of different production types.

Table 4

Amount of body parts in relation to semi-meat, kg

<i>Parts</i>	<i>Group (p=3)</i>	
	<i>I</i>	<i>II</i>
Neck	9.4	8.5
Shoulders	22.1	21.4
Back and ribs	35.1	41.4
Waist	10.6	10.5
Pelvis	43.3	46.2
Total	120.5	128.0

As can be seen from the data of table 4, when studying the meatni variety pieces , the first quality piece in group II was 98.1 kg, this indicator was 89.0 kg in group I, and the bulls in group II were 9.1 kg or 10.2%. achieved a high rate. When the bulls of the second grade were studied, it was 21.4 kg in group II and 22.1 kg in group I , and it was 0.7 kg or 3.2% less in bulls of the second group. Third grade bulls weighed 8.5 kg in group II and 9.4 kg in group I , and 0.9 kg or 9.6% less was observed in bulls of the second group. From these data, it can be seen that high-quality pieces of meat were obtained from bulls of the II group (meat-milk type). This indicates that quality meat is obtained from bulls of the meat-milk type.

Summary. All the bulls raised in intensive technology belonged to the first obesity category. Compared to live weight after fattening, during transport (150 km, 3 hours) and storage to slaughter (21 hours), group I lost 24.1 kg (5.3%) and group II 23.9 kg (4.9 %) live weight. . It can be said at the standard level. Live weight of bulls after weaning was 508.9 kg in group II (meat-milk type) and 479.4 kg in group I (milk-meat type), and bulls in the second group were 29.5 kg or 5.8% more than their counterparts in the first group. ($R \leq 0.001$) prevailed. When the morphological composition of the meat was studied, the presence of muscle tissue in a high percentage (74.2-74.4%) in both groups indicated that they had a high level of meat productivity. When the level of fullness of the half body was studied, the level of

fullness of meat was high in the neck, shoulders, back and ribs, waist, pelvis in both groups . When the quality pieces of meat were studied, high quality pieces of meat were obtained in large quantities from bulls of the II group (meat-milk type).

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